

Isotope Effect on Initial Retention of ^{80}Br , $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br in some Bromate Systems

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The initial retention of different bromine isotopes namely ^{80}Br , $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br for neutron activated alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal bromates were studied under identical conditions of neutron activation. The initial retention of ^{80}Br was always lower than that of $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br isotopes. The results clearly show the dependence of the retention on the nature of the cation.

Vast amount of data have been accumulated on recoil bromine atoms with special reference to retention studies^{1,2}. However, studies on initial retention of ^{80}Br , $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br made under identical conditions of irradiation are missing. It is of interest to examine the same in a number of bromate systems neutron activated under identical conditions and to understand the isotope effect involved therein.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained for the ^{80}Br , $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br isotopes produced simultaneously in each bromate system following neutron activations, are presented in Table 1. Each retention value is the average of at least 3 independent experiments and the standard deviation was $\pm 2\%$ (absolute) in the case of ^{80}Br isotope. It is evident from the variation in retention with respect to these isotopes that the isotope effect does exist. Further, it is noteworthy that the retention of ^{80}Br is always lower than the retentions of $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br and the value for ^{82}Br is considerably higher in most of the systems than those for the other two isotopes.

Difference in retention values of ^{82}Br and ^{80}Br may be taken as a measure of the isotope effect. This difference is profound in the case of transition metal bromates and it is largest for nickel bromate (14%). In alkali and alkaline earth metal bromates the difference is only 5–10%. Jach and Harbottle³, on the other hand, observed identical initial retentions of $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br isotopes in Na, K, Rb and Cs bromates; they found only retention rates differing upon subsequent heating.

The recoil energy being very high, the differences in it in the case of ^{80}Br , $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br isotopes cannot account for the observed isotope effect. Our results indicate that different modes of

nuclear de-excitation may be the principle origin of the isotope effect. In the isomeric transition $^{82\text{m}}\text{Br} \rightarrow ^{82}\text{Br}$, the $^{82\text{m}}\text{Br}$ atom attains a highly positive charge state as a result of emission of a conversion electron accompanying Auger electrons. The extensively increased charge on the nucleus subsequently being shared by the other atoms in the molecules in the bromate species, results an explosion of the species. Energy released in such coulombic explosion may be stored at the damaged recoil sites. As the structure gets partially restored, this energy may get released to bring about higher recombination events. Further, although there is no evidence³ of longlived states in the (n,γ) cascade populating $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$, components of low energies are likely to be present⁴ which may lead to internal conversion and subsequent Coulombic explosion followed by Auger charging as in the case of $^{82\text{m}}\text{Br} \rightarrow ^{82}\text{Br}$ transition. Hence additional recombinations can take place in the case of $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ as well. The isomeric transition phenomenon being absent in the case of ^{80}Br isotope, which is produced directly in the recoil process, retention observed here is lower.

Table 1 shows that the ^{80}Br retention depends on the nature of the cation. The values with respect to ^{80}Br isotope reveal that alkali metal bromates yield higher retention as compared to alkaline earth and transition metal bromates. The alkali metal bromates under investigation are anhydrous (except lithium) and show almost comparable values; while the alkaline earth metal bromates exhibit minimum ^{80}Br retention and the values for different systems again are practically identical. The transition metal bromates also show identical values. The modes of thermal decomposition of these three different types of metal bromates are different⁵. The alkali and alkaline earth metal bromates form a bromide on decomposition while the transition metal bromates form an oxide. This indicates that the

decomposition of bromates brought about as a consequence of the (n, γ) activation also differs depending upon the nature of the cation. The geminate recombination processes that follows may therefore be different and yield the subsequent bromate in different proportions. These considerations throw light on the observed retention trends. This discussion is applicable primarily to ^{80}Br retention; the $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br retentions having larger deviations due to low counting rates, are not considered here.

TABLE 1.—INITIAL RETENTION VALUES (%) OBTAINED FOR ^{80}Br , $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ AND ^{82}Br ISOTOPES USING ^{252}Cf SOURCE FOR NEUTRON ACTIVATION AT 25°

Compd.	^{80}Br	$^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$	^{82}Br	(C - A) (C - B)	
	(A)	(B)	(C)		
LiBrO ₃ ·H ₂ O	20.0	19.5	21.0	1.0	1.5
NaBrO ₃	18.1	22.0	28.1	10.0	6.1
KBrO ₃	19.0	24.0	25.5	6.5	1.5
RbBrO ₃	20.2	16.7	20.2	0.0	3.5
Mg(BrO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	14.8	16.2	20.1	5.3	3.9
Ca(BrO ₃) ₂ ·H ₂ O	14.7	17.9	20.3	5.6	2.4
Sr(BrO ₃) ₂ ·H ₂ O	11.3	19.9	21.6	10.3	1.7
Ba(BrO ₃) ₂ ·H ₂ O	14.1	16.4	20.9	6.8	4.5
Ni(BrO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	16.8	19.2	30.9	14.1	11.7
Zn(BrO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	17.0	19.3	26.5	9.5	7.2
Cd(BrO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	14.2	18.0	20.8	6.6	2.8

Experimental

Most of the bromates were synthesised⁶ by double decomposition of respective metal sulphate and barium bromate monohydrate. After the addition of solutions containing calculated quantities of Li, Rb, Mg, Ni, Zn or Cd sulphate and barium bromate, small aliquots of the solution were tested for complete precipitation by adding alternatively the metal sulphate and barium bromate solutions. After digestion (2 h) the supernatant solution containing the desired bromate was concentrated, filtered to remove the remaining BaSO₄ and finally slowly evaporated at 50°. After chilling to ice temperature, the resulting microcrystalline powder was recrystallised using minimum amount of water, dried over P₂O₅ and stored in a desiccator.

Calcium and strontium bromates were synthesised by boiling a slurry of excess amount of barium bromate monohydrate and the Ca or Sr sulphate; about 15 h of boiling were needed in the former case and about 70 h in the latter. Water was added time to time to compensate the loss due to evaporation. Following decantation and filtration,

the solution containing the desired bromate was concentrated by slow evaporation at about 60°. The bromates were then recrystallised using minimum quantity of distilled water, dried over P₂O₅ and stored in a desiccator.

Purity of the compounds was determined by estimating⁷ their bromate, cation and water contents. The cation component was determined volumetrically by EDTA titration. Information regarding the amount of water molecules lost on heating was obtained from the thermogravimetry data. The bromate was estimated by iodometric method. The purity was found to be >98% in all the preparations.

Neutron activation was effected using a ^{252}Cf fission neutron source (flux: $\sim 10^7 \text{ n cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and γ -dose: 0.2 rad s^{-1}). For the chemical separation of bromate and non-bromate species, solvent extraction technique was used⁸. Activity was measured by a liquid G.M. counter. The total activity of the three isotopes was counted immediately after separation, i.e. within 5 min from the removal of the sample from the source. Activity of $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ and ^{82}Br was counted together 2.5 h after the separation, the activity left over after 36 h was determined as that of ^{82}Br . For this use was made of both liquid G.M. counter and a γ -ray spectrometer which were precalibrated against each other. A computer programme was developed for applying the decay corrections of these isotopes and evaluation of retention values.

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